

A New GPU Implementation of Support Vector Machines for Fast Hyperspectral Image Classification

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Abstract: The storage and processing of remotely sensed hyperspectral images (HSIs) is facing important challenges due to the computational requirements involved in the analysis of these images, characterized by continuous and narrow spectral channels. Although HSIs offer many opportunities for accurately modeling and mapping the surface of the Earth in a wide range of applications, they comprise massive data cubes. These huge amounts of data impose important requirements from the storage and processing points of view. The support vector machine (SVM) has been one of the most powerful machine learning classifiers, able to process HSI data without applying previous feature extraction steps, exhibiting a robust behaviour with high dimensional data and obtaining high classification accuracies. Nevertheless, the training and prediction stages of this supervised classifier are very time-consuming, especially for large and complex problems that require an intensive use of memory and computational resources. This paper develops a new, highly efficient implementation of SVMs that exploits the high computational power of graphics processing units (GPUs) to reduce the execution time by massively parallelizing the operations of the algorithm while performing efficient memory management during data-reading and writing instructions. Our experiments, conducted over different HSI benchmarks, demonstrate the efficiency of our GPU implementation.

Keywords: Hyperspectral images (HSIs), support vector machines (SVMs), graphics processing units (GPUs), hardware parallelization.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in computer technology have allowed for the development of powerful instruments for remote sensed data acquisition, lowering both the cost of their production and the cost of launching new Earth Observation (EO) missions. In particular, imaging spectroscopy (also known as hyperspectral imaging) [1] has attracted the attention of many researchers because of the great potential of hyperspectral images (HSIs) in characterizing the surface of the Earth by covering the visible, near-infrared and shortwave infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. To exploit these data, multiple EO missions are now using imaging spectrometers, such as the *Environmental Mapping and Analysis Programme* (EnMAP) [2,3], or the *Hyperspectral Precursor of the Application Mission* (PRISMA) [4]. In this context, a high-dimensional stream of remotely sensed HSI data is now being generated, which can be applied to multiple tasks after being properly processed, such as managing of natural and environmental resources, urban planning and monitoring of agricultural fields, risk prevention and natural/human disaster management, among others.

However, HSI data processing faces important memory and computational requirements, due the large amount of information provided by EO airborne/satellite instruments. In fact, imaging spectrometers are able to collect hundreds of images over large areas along the Earth's surface, gathering hundreds of narrow and continuous spectral bands along different wavelengths. As a result, each pixel in a HSI cube measures the reflection and absorption of electromagnetic radiation from

36 ground objects into several spectral channels, creating a unique spectral signature for each material
37 optically detected by the spectrometer [5]. This allows for a very accurate characterization of land
38 cover surface, which is useful for the modeling and mapping of materials of interest but presents
39 significant computational requirements. In particular, spectral-based classification algorithms need to
40 process large amounts of spectral information in order to correctly assign a label (which corresponds
41 to a fixed land cover class) to each pixel in the HSI scene, facing heavy computation burdens [6]. In
42 this sense, the development of parallel implementations of traditional classification algorithms for fast
43 and accurate processing is a requirement in order to efficiently process large HSI data repositories
44 through proper management of computational resources.

45 With this aim, high performance computing (HPC) has become an efficient tool, not only for
46 managing and analyzing the increasing amount of remotely sensed data that are currently being
47 collected [7–10], but also for efficiently dealing with the high dimensionality of HSI data cubes [11,12].
48 From a computational point of view, most spectral-based HSI data classification algorithms exhibit
49 inherent parallelism at three different levels [13]:

- 50 • through HSI pixel vectors (coarse-grained pixel level parallelism),
- 51 • through spectral-band information (fine-grained spectral level parallelism), and
- 52 • through tasks (task-level parallelism).

53 HSI classification algorithms generally map nicely on HPC systems [14], with several HPC approaches
54 (from coarse-grained and fine-grained parallelism techniques to complex distributed environments)
55 already successfully implemented. For instance, distributed approaches based on commodity
56 (homogeneous and heterogeneous) clusters [15,16], grid computing [17,18], and cloud computing
57 techniques [19–22] have provided good results in terms of reducing execution times, enabling an
58 efficient processing of massive data sets on the ground segment. However, dedicated resources such as
59 massively parallel clusters and networks of computers are generally expensive and hard to maintain,
60 being cloud computing a more appropriate and cheaper approach (in addition to a fully distributed
61 solution) due to its “service-oriented” computing and “pay-per-use” model [23]. Neither cluster nor
62 cloud computing models allow on-board processing.

63 On the other hand, parallel solutions based on multicore CPUs [10,24,25], graphics processing
64 units (GPUs) [14,26–29], and field programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) [30–34] have also been successful,
65 leading to near real-time performance in many HSI applications [35]. These platforms generally provide
66 a cheaper solution when compared to large-scale distributed systems. Also, these approaches consume
67 much less energy in comparison with cluster-based or distributed systems, being GPU systems (in
68 particular, those with low-power consumption [36]) and FPGAs the ones currently offering the best
69 performance/consumption ratio. Nevertheless, although both kinds of devices are appealing for
70 on-board processing, FPGAs (despite their reconfigurability) are still more difficult to program than
71 GPUs. In fact, GPUs are massively parallel programmable systems that can satisfy the extremely high
72 computational requirements by HSI-based applications at low cost, with very good programmability.
73 As a result, many HSI data processing algorithms have been implemented on GPUs, including target
74 and anomaly detection methods [37,38], and techniques for image compression [39], scene classification
75 [40], and spectral unmixing [41].

76 In this paper, we develop a new GPU implementation of the traditional support vector machine
77 (SVM) algorithm [42]. Traditionally considered as a powerful classifier in a wide variety of fields, such
78 as medical computing or text and image processing (among others), the SVM has been successfully
79 adopted in HSI classification problems. It separates two classes of samples with the maximal margin
80 by exploiting an optimal decision boundary [43]. As a result, SVMs have often been found to
81 provide higher classification accuracies than other widely used pattern recognition techniques, such
82 as the maximum likelihood, the random forest (RF) or the multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifiers.
83 Furthermore, SVMs appear to be particularly advantageous in heterogeneous environments, for which
84 only a few training samples are available per class. The SVM has demonstrated its success in HSI data
85 classification in a multitude of scientific works within the remote sensing field [44] due to its robust

86 behaviour when dealing with high-dimensional data and its great ability to generalize to unseen data.
 87 However, SVMs exhibit a high computational cost, which strongly discourages its use when facing
 88 large-scale, real-time HSI classification problems.

89 To mitigate the aforementioned problem, several techniques have been adopted to reduce the
 90 execution time of SVMs. For instance, in [45], Osuna *et al.* presented a decomposition algorithm by
 91 addressing sub-problems iteratively to enable tackling larger problems. In [46], Platt proposed the
 92 sequential minimal optimization (SMO) algorithm by decomposing the quadratic programming (QP)
 93 problem into a series of smaller QP subproblems that can be solved analytically, without the need for a
 94 time-consuming QP optimization. Ease of implementation is a typical feature of the SMO algorithm.
 95 In [47], Fan *et al.* developed a series of working set selection (WSS) heuristics, based on second order
 96 information, to achieve a faster convergence of the SMO. Recently, some researchers utilized the
 97 portability and excellent computing performance of GPUs to address the computational requirements
 98 of SVMs. Particularly, Tan *et al.* [48] proposed a novel two-level parallel computing framework based
 99 on NVIDIA's compute device unified architecture (CUDA) and OpenMP to accelerate SVM-based
 100 classification, while Li *et al.* [49] utilized GPU devices to improve the speed performance of SVM
 101 training and prediction stages.

102 In this work, we present a novel GPU implementation of SVMs that does not only reduces
 103 the execution time by massively parallelizing the operations of the algorithm on the GPU, but also
 104 performing efficient memory management during data-reading and writing operations [50]. We
 105 empirically evaluate the efficiency of our method considering different HSI real scenes, which comprise
 106 urban and agricultural land-cover information, and observed that it is able to maintain the precision in
 107 the results while significantly improving the computational performance.

108 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the fundamentals
 109 of the SVM method adapted to HSI data. Section 3 describes the GPU implementation of the
 110 considered classifier. Section 4 validates the GPU implementation by comparing it with other existing
 111 implementations. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with some remarks and hints at plausible
 112 future research lines.

113 2. Support Vector Machines (SVMs): A Review

114 2.1. Linear SVM

115 Any HSI classification method $y = f(\mathbf{x})$ can be described as the mapping function $f : \mathbb{N}^{n_b} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$,
 116 where the domain is composed by those spectral pixels $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{N}^{n_b} = [x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{in_b}]$ that encode the
 117 reflectance values of the HSI cube $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{N}^{n_h \times n_w \times n_b}$, which is composed by $n_h \cdot n_w$ pixels (note that
 118 $i = \{1, \dots, n_h \cdot n_w\}$) with n_b spectral bands, while the co-domain is composed by the corresponding
 119 label-vectors $y_i \in [1, 2, \dots, n_c]$, being n_c the number of different land cover categories. The final goal
 120 is to obtain the sample-label pairs for each HSI image element, $\{\mathbf{x}_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^{n_h \cdot n_w}$, obtaining as a result the
 121 final classification map $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{N}^{n_h \times n_w}$.

In this context, the original SVM method [51] was proposed for binary classification problems, i.e.
 $n_c = 2$ so $y_i \in \{1, -1\}$, $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_h \cdot n_w\}$, where the two considered classes are linearly separable,
 with at least one hyperplane separating them (see Fig. 1). This hyperplane is defined by its *normal*
vector $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_b}$ and the *bias* $b \in \mathbb{R}$ that defines the distance between the samples and the hyperplane.
 In this regard, the classifier can be defined as the discriminant function:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{w}\mathbf{x} + b, \quad (1)$$

where $f(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ is the hyperplane and the samples lie on the planes $f(\mathbf{x}) = \pm 1$ depending on the
 class they belong to. Both parameters \mathbf{w} and b are estimated by the SVM during the training stage in
 order to maximize the distance between the closest sample and the hyperplane, i.e. with the aim of
 maximizing the margin $m = 2/\|\mathbf{w}\|$ [42]. This maximization problem should be conveniently replaced

Figure 1. General SVM scheme. The final goal is to approximate parameters \mathbf{w} and b with the aim of defining the optimal hyperplane that maximizes the margin between the two classes

by the equivalent minimization problem $\frac{1}{2}\|\mathbf{w}\|^2$. In the end, the SVM finds the optimal hyperplane along the space of samples by minimizing the *quadratic optimization problem* given by Eq. (2):

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}, b} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2, \quad \text{subject to } y_i (\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x}_i + b) - 1 \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_t\} \quad (2)$$

where n_t is the number of training samples, \mathbf{x}_i is the i -th sample, and y_i is the correct output provided by the SVM, i.e. +1 for positive samples and -1 for negative ones. Considering the Lagrangian formulation [52], Eq. (2) can be simplified by replacing the inequality \geq through a dual problem. In particular, employing the Lagrange multipliers $\alpha_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_t\}$, we define the optimization problem given by Eq. (3), which only depends on the set of Lagrange multipliers $\alpha = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{n_t}\}$:

$$\min_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \sum_{j=1}^{n_t} y_i y_j (\mathbf{x}_i \cdot \mathbf{x}_j) \alpha_i \alpha_j - \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i, \quad \text{subject to } \alpha_i \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} y_i \alpha_i = 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_t\}, \quad (3)$$

122 where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j are two samples of the training set with labels y_i and y_j and Lagrange multipliers α_i
 123 and α_j , respectively. Eq. (3) can be computed using QP methods, such as the SMO [53], which breaks
 124 the problem into a series of smallest and equivalent QP problems, solving each one analytically.

With this problem representation, the normal vector \mathbf{w} can be derived as the sum of all the samples that belong to the training set and modified by their corresponding Lagrange multiplier together with the associated class of the sample, $\mathbf{w} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i y_i \mathbf{x}_i$, while the bias is obtained for some multiplier $\alpha_j > 0$ as $b = \mathbf{w} \mathbf{x}_j - y_j$. Moreover, the discriminant function $f(\mathbf{x})$ provided by Eq. (1) can be solely described in terms of Lagrange multipliers and samples as:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i y_i (\mathbf{x}_i \cdot \mathbf{x}) + b \quad (4)$$

125

126 It is worth noting that each Lagrange multiplier α_i measures the relevance of the sample \mathbf{x}_i when
 127 calculating the hyperplane and classifying the data, so that samples with $\alpha_i = 0$ will be ignored, while
 128 samples with $\alpha_i > 0$ will be considered as *support vectors*. Also, from Eq. (4), we can observe that, to

Figure 2. In order to deal with non-linearly separable data, the SVM applies a transformation Φ to translate the data from the original non-linear representation in space \mathbb{N}^{nb} , to a linear representation in space \mathcal{H} , i.e. $\Phi : \mathbb{N}^{nb} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$

129 perform the classification of any sample \mathbf{x} , a significant volume of memory will be required, consuming
 130 also a large amount of computational resources to compute the dot products needed.

131 2.2. Linear SVM for Linearly-Nonseparable Data Classification

The linear SVM has a limitation: with linearly-nonseparable data classification there may not be a hyperplane, so the solution becomes infinite. To overcome this drawback, the linear soft-margin SVM implements a new cost function, which takes into account the original margin maximization and including a loss term that penalizes misclassified data, as it can be observed in Eq. (5):

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}, b} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \delta_i, \quad \text{subject to } y_i (\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x}_i + b) - 1 + \delta_i \geq 0 \text{ and } \delta_i \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

132 where $\delta_i \geq 0$ are some *slack variables* that are introduced into the inequality restriction $y_i (\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x}_i + b) -$
 133 $1 + \delta_i \geq 0$ to relax the condition that all the samples that belongs to the same class lie on the same side
 134 of the hyperplane. Thus, $\sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \delta_i$ can be interpreted as some measure of the amount of misclassifications.

135 Also, a regularization constant $C \in [0, \infty)$ is included to control the weight of minimizing $\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2$
 136 while penalizing solutions with very large δ_i . In fact, C can be considered as a parameter that adjusts
 137 the robustness or flexibility of the model, depending its value.

138 Once more, the Lagrangian formulation can be applied to translate the primal problem defined
 139 by Eq. (5) into the dual problem of Eq. (3), by simply introducing the box constraint $C \geq \alpha_i \geq 0$. The
 140 slack variables δ_i do not affect the optimization problem.

141 2.3. Kernel SVM for Non-Linear Data Classification

As an alternative to the soft-margin implementation, the SVM method can be adapted to perform non-linear classification by including a kernel [54,55] within the classifier. The main idea is to map the original feature vectors $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{N}^{nb}$ into a higher dimensional Euclidean space, denoted as \mathcal{H} , by using a non-linear vector function $\Phi : \mathbb{N}^{nb} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$, as we can observe in Fig. 2. In this context, the optimal margin problem can be posed in the space \mathcal{H} by replacing the original inner product between the

samples $\mathbf{x}_i \cdot \mathbf{x}$ with the transformed vectors $\Phi(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \Phi(\mathbf{x})$, so the discriminant function will be defined as:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i y_i (\Phi(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \Phi(\mathbf{x})) + b \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Replacing } K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) = \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \Phi(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i y_i K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) + b$$

Eq. (6) can be easily simplified by assuming there is such a kernel function that $K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) = \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \Phi(\mathbf{x})$. This assumption allows to avoid the computation of the inner product between transformed vectors, significantly reducing the computational consumption of the algorithm. To ensure the existence of the underlying map Φ , the kernel function is positively defined [51] by satisfying Mercer's conditions [56].

Finally, the solution of the dual problem can be also meaningfully simplified as:

$$\min_{\alpha} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \sum_{j=1}^{n_t} y_i y_j K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) \alpha_i \alpha_j - \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i, \quad \text{subject to } C \geq \alpha_i \geq 0 \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} y_i \alpha_i = 0 \quad (7)$$

In fact, the kernel function usually measures the distance between the input sample \mathbf{x}_i and the other training samples \mathbf{x}_j . Table 1 shows some of the most widely used kernels. In particular, the RBF kernel has quite interesting properties. It can be simplified as $\exp(-\gamma \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^2)$, where γ controls the model's performance, in the sense that a small value of γ will provide classification solutions with low bias and high variance, while a high value of γ will give solutions with high bias and low variance.

Table 1. Most common kernels in the SVM method, where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j are two samples of dataset \mathbf{X} .

Linear	$\langle \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle$
Polynomial	$(\gamma \langle \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle + c)^n$
Gaussian	$\exp(-\gamma \ \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\ ^2) \gamma$
Sigmoid	$\tanh(\gamma \langle \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j \rangle + c)^n$
Radial basis function (RBF)	$\exp\left(-\frac{\ \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\ ^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$

151

152 2.4. Multi-class SVM

The aforementioned SVM implementations can be generalized to develop multi-class classification by combining several binary classifiers [42]. In this regard, there are two main strategies that can be adopted to perform multi-class classification [57]: i) constructing and combining several binary classifiers, and ii) considering all data in one optimization formulation.

Regarding the first approach, it is usual to find *one-against-all*, *one-against-one* and *decision directed acyclic graph* (DDAG)-based approaches for multi-class SVM in the available literature [58–60]. The first approach constructs n_c pairwise classifiers, where the k -th model is trained with those samples that belong to the k -th class by assigning them a positive label (while the rest of the samples are paired with negative labels). The classification procedure applies the n_c SVM models to each sample \mathbf{x}_i , selecting the label of the classifier $f_k(\mathbf{x})$ with the largest margin:

$$y_i = \arg \max_k f_k(\mathbf{x}_i) \quad (8)$$

As a result, n_c n_t -variable QP-problems have to be solved, which implies that training time scales linearly with n_c . Instead of developing n_c classifiers, the *one-against-one* approach adopts a pairwise decomposition strategy, implementing $n_c(n_c - 1)/2$ binary models on all pairs of training data. Each model f_{kt} is trained on data that belong to two different classes, k and t , ignoring all the other classes.

In this way, those samples that belong to class k are labeled as positive, while the samples that belong to class t correspond to the negative label (note that $f_{tk} = -f_{kt}$). The final label is selected by majority voting strategy:

$$y_i = \arg \max_k \left(\sum_t f_{kt}(\mathbf{x}_i) \right) \quad (9)$$

157 It is noteworthy that the one-against-one approach exhibits a much more robust behaviour when
158 classifying imbalanced datasets, however, it is also more computationally expensive than the
159 one-against-all for simpler problems, such as those with fewer classes.

160 Finally, the DDAGSVM also solves $n_c(n_c - 1)/2$ binary models during the training stage,
161 implementing a rooted binary directed acyclic graph with also $n_c(n_c - 1)/2$ internal nodes (each
162 one is a binary SVM) and n_c leaves (i.e. the predicted class) during the testing stage.

163 3. GPU-Accelerated SVM for HSI Data Classification

164 3.1. Previous works and proposal overview

165 Despite obtaining great accuracy results, the training and prediction steps of the SVM algorithm
166 are very expensive from a computational point of view, especially for large and complex problems.
167 Furthermore, it is noteworthy that kernel-based techniques can greatly simplify the computations,
168 thus reducing the execution times. However, these methods need to use all the data to properly
169 calculate the kernel, which generally requires large memory consumption [61]. In particular, HSI data
170 offers a great challenge to the SVM classifier, mainly due to (both) the large spectral dimensionality
171 and volume of data to be processed. As noted in Section 1, there have been some previous works
172 in the literature focused on optimizing and parallelizing the execution of the SVM. However, there
173 are few efforts in the recent literature oriented to the exploitation of GPU-based implementations
174 for HSI data classification. From the current state-of-the-art in the literature, we can highlight two
175 works. Tan *et al.* [48] combined the NVIDIA Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) [50] and
176 OpenMP [62] to optimize the classification problem, and implemented as a multi-class SVM following
177 one-against-one strategy. In this sense, they were able to run the one-against-one strategy in parallel
178 by implementing an OpenMP-based approach, while each single WSS-based binary SVM classifier
179 was parallelized into GPUs. In addition, the calculation of every kernel element $K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$ was done
180 by the GPU, being the constant values stored into the shared memory of the GPU device, following
181 column-major order, and sent (when needed) through a broadcasting mechanism. Also, Wu *et al.*
182 [63] developed a GPU-parallelized SVM method based on composite kernels (SVMCK) [64] and able
183 to integrate spatial and spectral information, with the aim of improving the accuracy in HSI data
184 classification tasks. In this context, they carried the calculations of the composite kernel matrix in the
185 GPU. The resulting $K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$ were copied to the host (CPU), and then stored in the available memory
186 of the host. The rest of the computations were carried out in the CPU.

187 In this context, we propose a new parallel version of the SVM algorithm for high dimensionality
188 data. Our proposal can be efficiently generalized to be applied in other fields, being our parallel SVM
189 adapted to the specific case of remote sensing HSI data classification. In particular, we propose a
190 parallel implementation of a multi-class SVM, following one-against-one strategy, with the RBF kernel.
191 It must be noted that each single binary SVM has been solved through the SMO method. Furthermore,
192 the SMO solver (during the training stage) and the full inference stage have been paralleled into a
193 general purpose GPU (GPGPU) framework, employing the NVIDIA CUDA platform. Our goal is not
194 only to achieve a good speed up ratio in comparison with other traditional SVM implementations, but
195 also to develop a scalable implementation with regards to both the amount of data and the spectral
196 dimensionality of the data. In this regard, the implemented approach performs the algorithmic
197 parallelization of the SVM operations during the training and inference stages, implementing at the
198 same time a series of optimizations in the memory read and write operations, with the aim of reducing

Figure 3. Programming and memory model provided by NVIDIA CUDA for a GPU device.

199 the number of communications between the host and the device, and to reduce the memory latency.
 200 Also, it should be noted that a data-oriented parallelization strategy has been adopted, parallelizing the
 201 operations related to data management and reusing as much information as possible between different
 202 iterations. Regarding to this, a batch-based approach has been implemented within the SMO with the
 203 aim of solving multiple sub-problems in parallel. Particular attention has been paid to the calculation
 204 of the kernel matrix, as it consumes a massive amount of computational and storage resources. In the
 205 following sections we will provide details about our new implementation.

206 3.2. CUDA platform

207 In order to obtain an accelerated version of the SVM for HSI data classification, a GPGPU-based
 208 implementation has been employed using NVIDIA CUDA platform [50]. The main goal is to exploit
 209 the full computing power of GPU devices (using the general-purpose parallel computing platform
 210 and the programming model offered by CUDA) to solve many complex computational problems
 211 in a more efficient way. Specifically, we solve n_c binary SVM instances (with the RBF kernel) that
 212 compose our multi-class SVM algorithm for remote sensing HSI data classification. In this context, we
 213 consider the GPU device as a set of stream multiprocessors, composed by several cores with a 3-level
 214 hierarchical memory system: i) several fast registers that are accessible by each stream processor, ii) a
 215 multiprocessor-level memory that is shared between all the cores that compose the multiprocessor,
 216 and iii) a global memory shared between all the multiprocessors.

217 As we can observe in Fig. 3, CUDA maintains the hierarchy of memories at the same time
 218 that provides a programming model which abstracts the system of cores and multiprocessors into
 219 a three-level logical representation of *threads*, *blocks* and *grids*, where the thread is the minimum
 220 processing unit (that can be grouped into 1D/2D/3D blocks of warps), and the blocks can be
 221 organized into a 1D/2D grid environment. In this sense, the programmer determines the logical
 222 representation by organizing the structure of the threads in the grid that best fits the data structure
 223 handled by the problem to be parallelized. Underneath, CUDA maps this representation to the actual
 224 hardware resources. This distinction between physical and logical representations allows CUDA-based
 225 algorithms to be ported to any NVIDIA GPU platform, improving their scalability and computing
 226 performance as new and higher-capacity GPUs are released to the market. In addition, it should be
 227 highlighted that each thread has access to three different memory spaces: its local memory, the memory
 228 shared by all the threads of the same block, and the global memory shared by all the threads of the

229 grid. Therefore the correct handling of the threads and their accesses to memory are fundamental for
 230 the correct and optimal parallelization of the problem.

231 Through the organization and synchronization of the threads, we can develop the parallel
 232 processing of the operations carried out by the SVM method. In particular, we can differentiate
 233 between those operations performed during the training stage of the SVM and those operations
 234 performed during the inference step.

235 3.3. Parallel SMO During the Training Stage

236 3.3.1. Previous concepts about the SMO algorithm

As pointed out before, we have adopted the one-against-one approach for the multi-class SVM to perform remote sensing HSI data classification. Therefore $n_c(n_c - 1)/2$ binary models must be properly trained to extract the support vectors and derive the corresponding Lagrange multipliers for each classifier. Particularly, the binary models have been trained using a decomposition method to solve the convex optimization problem defined by Eq. (7). It is noticeable that the main difficulty when solving Eq. (7) is how to calculate the kernel matrix $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_t \times n_t}$ that stores the kernel values $K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$, $\forall i \in [1, n_t]$ and $\forall j \in [1, n_t]$, as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} K(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_1) & K(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) & \cdots & K(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_{n_t}) \\ K(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_1) & K(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_2) & \cdots & K(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_{n_t}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ K(\mathbf{x}_{n_t}, \mathbf{x}_1) & K(\mathbf{x}_{n_t}, \mathbf{x}_2) & \cdots & K(\mathbf{x}_{n_t}, \mathbf{x}_{n_t}) \end{pmatrix}$$

237 Usually, \mathbf{K} is a dense matrix and may be too difficult to be efficiently stored and handled if n_t is too
 238 large. To deal with this limitation, some decomposition methods have been designed [46,47,65–74] to
 239 break down the problem into several smaller and easier to handle sub-problems, where small subsets
 240 of Lagrange variables α are modified by employing some columns of \mathbf{K} instead of the entire matrix.
 241 Particularly, the SMO [46] algorithm has been considered in this work.

The SMO is a simple and iterative algorithm that allows for the quick and effective resolution of very large QP problems (such as those involved in the SVM calculations) by decomposing such overall QP problem into smaller QP sub-problems [45], which are solved analytically without the need for numerical optimization. It solves the optimization problem described by Eqs. (3) and (7), by solving the smallest possible optimization problem at every step until the optimal condition of the SVM classifier is reached. As the linear equality constraint $\sum_{i=1}^{n_t} y_i \alpha_i = 0$ involves the Lagrange multipliers α_i , the smallest possible optimization problem will involve two such multipliers, in the sense that, if we change one α_t by an amount in either direction, then the same change must be applied to another α_l in the opposite direction. That is, α_t and α_l should be on the same line in order to maintain the constraint (see Fig. 4):

$$y_t \alpha_t + y_l \alpha_l = y_t \hat{\alpha}_t + y_l \hat{\alpha}_l, \text{ subject to } \alpha_t \geq 0 \text{ and } \alpha_l \geq C \quad (10)$$

242 In this way, the SMO algorithm comprises two main components: i) a heuristic for selecting the pair
 243 of Lagrange multipliers to be optimized, and ii) an analytic method for solving those multipliers. In
 244 this sense, in each iteration the SMO algorithm heuristically chooses two Lagrange multipliers α_t and
 245 α_l at every step to jointly optimize, then it analytically obtains the new optimal values $\hat{\alpha}_t$ and $\hat{\alpha}_l$, and
 246 finally it updates the SVM to reflect the new values.

Focusing on the heuristic procedure, the SMO applies two heuristic searches, one for each Lagrange multiplier. The first multiplier α_t is chosen by iterating over the entire training set, looking

Figure 4. The inequality constraint $C \geq \alpha_i \geq 0$ forces the Lagrange multipliers to be into a box while the linear equality constraint $\sum_{i=1}^{n_t} y_i \alpha_i = 0$ forces them to lie on a diagonal line. Therefore, one step of the SMO algorithm should find the optimum values $\hat{\alpha}_t$ and $\hat{\alpha}_l$ on a diagonal line segment.

for those samples that violate the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions [75] that help to find an optimal separating hyperplane. In particular, the KKT conditions for Eq. (7) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i = 0 &\Leftrightarrow y_i(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x}_i + b) \geq 1, \\ C > \alpha_i < 0 &\Leftrightarrow y_i(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x}_i + b) = 1, \\ \alpha_i = C &\Leftrightarrow y_i(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x}_i + b) \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where y_i is the correct SVM output and $(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x}_i + b)$ is the current output of the SVM for the i -th sample \mathbf{x}_i , $\forall i \in [1, n_t]$. Any α_i that satisfies the KKT conditions will be an optimal solution for the QP optimization problem defined by Eq. (7). On the contrary, any α_i that violates the KKT conditions will be eligible for optimization, so the SMO's goal is to iterate until all these conditions are satisfied within a tolerance threshold (in our case, this tolerance has been set to 0.001). Once the first α_t has been chosen, the second Lagrange multiplier α_l is selected in order to maximize the size of the step taken during joint optimization. To do this, the SMO method implements an *optimality indicator vector* $\mathbf{E} = [E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n_t}]$, where each E_j is the optimality indicator of the j -th training sample, i.e. the classification errors on the j -th sample:

$$E_j = f(\mathbf{x}_j) - y_j = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \alpha_i y_i K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) + b \right) - y_j \quad (12)$$

Related to this, α_t and α_l can be selected by looking for those samples \mathbf{x}_t and \mathbf{x}_l that have the maximum and minimum optimality indicators that maximize $|E_t - E_l|$, so if E_t is positive, the SMO will choose a sample with minimum E_l , while if E_t is negative, the SMO will select a sample with maximum E_l . The desired indexes t and l can be directly obtained by computing Eq. (13) [67]:

$$\begin{aligned} t &= \arg \min_i \{E_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}_{upper}\} \\ l &= \arg \max_i \left\{ \frac{(E_t - E_i)^2}{\mu_i} \mid E_t < E_i, \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}_{lower} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\mu_i = K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_i) - 2K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_i)$, E_t and E_i are the optimality indicator of samples \mathbf{x}_t and \mathbf{x}_i , respectively, and $\mathcal{X}_{upper} = \mathcal{X}_1 \cup \mathcal{X}_2 \cup \mathcal{X}_3$ and $\mathcal{X}_{lower} = \mathcal{X}_1 \cup \mathcal{X}_4 \cup \mathcal{X}_5$ are two data subsets, where each \mathcal{X}_* is composed by the following training samples:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{X}_1 &= \{\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}, 0 < \alpha_i < C\} \\ \mathcal{X}_2 &= \{\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}, y_i = +1, \alpha_i = 0\} \\ \mathcal{X}_3 &= \{\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}, y_i = -1, \alpha_i = C\} \\ \mathcal{X}_4 &= \{\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}, y_i = +1, \alpha_i = C\} \\ \mathcal{X}_5 &= \{\mathbf{x}_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}, y_i = -1, \alpha_i = 0\}\end{aligned}$$

247 Once both Lagrange multipliers have been obtained, the SMO method will compute their optimal
248 values $\hat{\alpha}_t$ and $\hat{\alpha}_l$ with the aim of obtaining the optimal class-separating hyperplane. In particular, it
249 begins by calculating $\hat{\alpha}_l$, whose feasible values are framed into the constraint $U \leq \hat{\alpha}_l \leq V$ to meet the
250 original $C \geq \alpha_l \geq 0$, being U and V two boundaries defined as:

$$251 \quad \text{If } y_t \neq y_l \begin{cases} U = \max\{0, \alpha_l - \alpha_t\} \\ V = \min\{C, C - \alpha_t + \alpha_l\} \end{cases} \quad (14) \quad \text{If } y_t = y_l \begin{cases} U = \max\{0, \alpha_t + \alpha_l - C\} \\ V = \min\{C, \alpha_t + \alpha_l\} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

252

Besides, the optimal $\hat{\alpha}_l$ value within the range $[U, V]$ will be obtained as:

$$\hat{\alpha}_l = \begin{cases} V, & \text{if } \tilde{\alpha}_l > V \\ \tilde{\alpha}_l, & \text{if } V \geq \tilde{\alpha}_l \geq U \text{ being } \tilde{\alpha}_l = \alpha_l + \frac{y_l(E_t - E_l)}{\mu} \\ U, & \text{if } \tilde{\alpha}_l < U \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $\mu = K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + K(\mathbf{x}_l, \mathbf{x}_l) - 2K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_l)$ and E_t and E_l are the classification errors on the t -th and l -th training samples respectively. Once $\hat{\alpha}_l$ has been obtained, an optimal $\hat{\alpha}_t$ is easily calculated as:

$$\hat{\alpha}_t = \alpha_t + y_t y_l (\alpha_l - \hat{\alpha}_l) \quad (17)$$

Once $\hat{\alpha}_t$ and $\hat{\alpha}_l$ have been obtained, the SMO updates the bias threshold b such that the KKT conditions are satisfied for the t -th and l -th samples. In this sense, three cases can occur, as we can observe in Eq. (18):

$$\hat{b} = \begin{cases} \hat{b}_1 & \text{if } C > \alpha_t > 0 \\ \hat{b}_2 & \text{if } C > \alpha_l > 0 \\ \frac{(\hat{b}_1 + \hat{b}_2)}{2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where \hat{b}_1 and \hat{b}_2 are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{b}_1 &= b - E_t - y_t(\hat{\alpha}_t - \alpha_t)K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) - y_l(\hat{\alpha}_l - \alpha_l)K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_l) \\ \hat{b}_2 &= b - E_l - y_t(\hat{\alpha}_t - \alpha_t)K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_l) - y_l(\hat{\alpha}_l - \alpha_l)K(\mathbf{x}_l, \mathbf{x}_l)\end{aligned}$$

Finally, the SMO updates the SVM. For each training sample \mathbf{x}_i , the SMO updates its E_i using the following Eq. (19):

$$E_i = E_i + (\hat{\alpha}_t - \alpha_t)y_t K(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_i) + (\hat{\alpha}_l)y_l K(\mathbf{x}_l, \mathbf{x}_i) \quad (19)$$

253 The full procedure is repeated until the optimal condition is reached, i.e. $E_t \geq E_{max}$, where E_{max} acts
254 as a threshold, $E_{max} = \max\{E_i | \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}_{lower}\}$.

255 3.3.2. CUDA optimization of SMO algorithm

256 The SVM starts by dividing the HSI scene into training and inference subsets. We can consider
257 the training set as a collection of instances and their associated labels, i.e. $\mathcal{D}_{train} = \{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}\}$. The training

instances are represented by a 2D-matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{N}^{n_t \times n_b}$ composed by n_t training vectors, where each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{N}^{n_b} = [x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}, \dots, x_{i,n_b}]$ comprises n_b spectral bands, while the training labels are stored into the matrix $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{N}^{n_t \times n_c}$, being $\mathbf{y}_i = [y_{i,1}, y_{i,2}, \dots, y_{i,n_c}]$ the corresponding label of sample \mathbf{x}_i in one-hot encoding, where n_c indicates the number of different land cover classes. The training stage starts by creating the different single binary SVMs in a sequential way, confronting each class i to each different class j , $\forall i, j \in [1, n_c]$. Each binary SVM has been optimized by employing a parallel SMO solver.

The parallel SMO solver begins by creating its working set B . Traditionally, B is of size two; however, our proposal implements a bigger working set to solve in parallel multiple subproblems of SMO in a batch. Moreover the proposed implementation precomputes all the kernel values for the current working set, storing them as a data buffer on the device's global memory, in order to reduce the high latency memory accesses and also to avoid a large number of small read/write operations in the CPU memory. This implies that, in each iteration of the SMO algorithm, the current working batch B will be updated, being n_B Lagrange multipliers optimized. This allows us to compute (at once) n_B rows of the kernel matrix \mathbf{K} , performing a more efficient use of the GPU by reducing the number of accesses to the device's global memory (which is much slower than the shared memory) and enabling the re-utilization of kernel information (which, in turn, reduces repeated kernel value computations). Taking this into account, our parallel SMO solver can be divided into three different steps.

During the **step 1**, the parallel SMO solver looks for the n_B extreme training instances which can potentially improve the SVM the most according to Eq. (9). This is parallelized by applying consecutive parallel reductions [76] over the training samples. For each working set, the optimality indicators of the training samples are sorted in ascending order, selecting the first $n_B/2$ and the last $n_B/2$ training samples to optimize the corresponding n_B Lagrange multipliers. During the reduction, one thread per sample takes the data from the global device memory to the block shared memory (in a coalesced way) to perform a fast execution. It must be noted that shared memory is around 7 times faster than global memory. Once synchronized, the threads operates over the data, where each one takes and compares the optimality indicators of the samples from the batch, choosing the smaller or the larger one depending on the desired Lagrange multiplier through the application of the corresponding heuristics given by Eq. (13).

Once the n_B Lagrange multipliers have been selected, the improvements of the Lagrangian multiplier pair α_t and α_l are sequentially obtained by one GPU thread per pair (**step 2**). It is worth noting from previous Eqs. (13), (16) and (19) that, during training stage, the same kernel values may be used in indifferent iterations. This implies that some kernel values can be stored into the GPU memory with the aim of reducing the high latency memory and avoiding a large number of small read/write operations from the CPU memory. In this sense, all the kernel values related to the n_B Lagrange multipliers are obtained, computing n_B rows of the kernel matrix \mathbf{K} through parallel matrix multiplications [77,78]:

$$\mathbf{K}_B = \begin{pmatrix} K(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_1) & K(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) & \cdots & K(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_{n_t}) \\ K(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_1) & K(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_2) & \cdots & K(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_{n_t}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ K(\mathbf{x}_{n_B}, \mathbf{x}_1) & K(\mathbf{x}_{n_B}, \mathbf{x}_2) & \cdots & K(\mathbf{x}_{n_B}, \mathbf{x}_{n_t}) \end{pmatrix}$$

In particular, the RBF-based \mathbf{K}_B matrix is computed in parallel by the GPU and stored into the device's global memory. Algorithm 1 provides the pseudo-code of the parallel kernel RBF function, which have been implemented following the approximate RBF kernel form:

$$K(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \exp\left(-\gamma \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^2\right) = \exp\left(-\gamma \left(\|\mathbf{x}_i\|^2 + \|\mathbf{x}_j\|^2 - 2\mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_j\right)\right) \quad (20)$$

286 In this context, the input parameters xx and $x2x$ contain the $\|x_i\|^2, \forall i \in [1, \dots, n_B]$ and $x_i x_j, \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, n_B]$ values respectively, which have been previously computed through parallel matrix multiplications [78]. Then, n_B threads compute the desired n_B rows of the kernel matrix \mathbf{K}_B :

Algorithm 1 Parallel Kernel RBF for HSI classification

Require: xx matrix of $\|x_i\|^2$ values,
 $x2x$ matrix of $x_i x_j$ values,
 K_B resulting kernel matrix,
 n_B number of rows,
 n_t number of training samples.

```

i = blockIdx.x * blockDim.x + threadIdx.x
if idx <  $n_B$  then
    j = 0
    while j <  $n_t$  do
         $K_B[i, j] = \exp(-\gamma(xx[i] + xx[j] - 2 * x2x[i, j]))$ 
        j ++
    end while
end if

```

288 During the training stage, the kernel values are extracted from the global memory and gathered
289 into the shared memory as they are needed, avoiding repeated computations.

291 Finally, the parallel SMO solver updates the optimality indicator vector \mathbf{E} of the training instances
292 by launching n_t GPU threads that compute Eq. (14) in parallel (step 3).

293 These training steps are sequentially repeated until the optimality condition is met or when the
294 SVM classifier is not able to improve.

295 3.4. Parallel classification during the inference stage

296 The proposed one-against-all SVM for HSI remote sensing data multi-class classification provides
297 the corresponding label y_i of a given test sample x_i by applying Eq. (8) during the inference stage. In
298 this sense, Eq. (8) is computed in parallel, making use of the kernel values in \mathbf{K} to reduce the latency
299 memory and avoid the repeated computations. Also, from Eq. (6) we can observe that $K(x_i, x_j)$ is
300 the same that $K(x_j, x_i)$, where i and j are related to the number of test samples and support vectors,
301 respectively. In this sense, we can reduce the number or read/copy operations into the GPU memory
302 following two strategies. On the one hand, if the number of test samples is larger than the number of
303 support vectors, we read all the rows of the kernel matrix \mathbf{K} that correspond to the support vectors by
304 reading the indexes respected to j . On the other hand, if the number of support vectors is larger than
305 the number of test samples, those rows that correspond to the test samples will be read by reading the
306 indexes respected to i .

307 4. Experimental Results

308 4.1. Experimental Environment

309 In order to evaluate the performance and the benefits of the proposed parallel SVM for HSI remote
310 sensing data classification, several implementations of the proposed classifier have been developed
311 and tested over two different hardware platforms:

- 312 1. **Platform 1:** it is composed by an Intel Core Coffee Lake Refresh i7-9750H processor, 32GB of
313 DDR4 RAM with 2667MHz, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 with 8GB of RAM, graphic clock
314 at 2100MHz and 14000MHZ of memory transfer rate. It is equipped with 2304 CUDA cores.
315 These processors have been named as CPU0 and GPU0.

316 2. **Platform 2:** Intel i9-9940X processor, 128GB of DDR4 RAM with 2100MHz, and an NVIDIA GTX
 317 1080Ti with 11GB of RAM, 2037MHz of graphic clock and 11232MHz of memory transfer rate. It
 318 is equipped with 3584 CUDA cores. These processors have been named as CPU1 and GPU1.

319 CPU1 will serve as the baseline for the performance comparisons that have been conducted during the
 320 experimentation due to its characteristics. Moreover, both environments use Ubuntu 18.04.3 x64 as
 321 operating system.

322 4.2. Hyperspectral Datasets

323 Our experiments have been conducted over six different and well-known HSI scenes: Indian
 324 Pines and Big Indian Pines, Pavia University, Salinas Valley and University of Houston. Table 5 shows
 325 the ground truth and the number of pixels per class for each image. Below, the characteristics of each
 326 scene are provided.

- 327 1. The first dataset is known as **Indian Pines**, which was collected by the Airborne Visible Infra-Red
 328 Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) [79] over the Indian Pines test site in North-western Indiana,
 329 which is characterized by several agricultural crops and irregular forest and pasture areas. It has
 330 145×145 pixels, each of which has 224 spectral reflectance bands covering the wavelengths from
 331 400nm to 2500nm. We remove the bands 104-108, 150-163 and 220 (water absorption and null
 332 bands), and keep 200 bands in our experiments. This scene has 16 different ground-truth classes
 333 (see Fig. 5).
- 334 2. **Big Indian Pines** is a larger version of the first dataset, which has 2678×614 pixels with
 335 wavelengths ranging from 400nm to 2500nm. We also remove the water absorption and null
 336 bands, retaining 200 spectral bands in our experiments. This scene has 58 ground-truth classes
 337 (see Fig. 5).
- 338 3. The third dataset is the **Pavia University** scene, which was collected by the Reflective Optics
 339 Spectrographic Imaging System (ROSIS) [80] during a flight campaign over Pavia, northern Italy.
 340 In this sense, it is characterized by being an urban area, with areas of buildings, roads and parking
 341 lots. In particular, the Pavia University scene has 610×340 pixels, and its spatial resolution is
 342 1.3m. The original pavia dataset contains 115 bands in the spectral region of 0.43-0.86 μm . We
 343 remove the water absorption bands, and retain 103 bands in our experiments. The number of
 344 classes in this scene is 9 (see Fig. 5).
- 345 4. The fourth dataset is **Pavia Centre** and was also gathered by ROSIS sensor. It is composed by
 346 1096×1096 pixels and 102 spectral bands. This scene also has 9 ground-truth classes from an
 347 urban area (see Fig. 5).
- 348 5. The fifth dataset is **Houston University** [81], which was acquired by the Compact Airborne
 349 Spectrographic Imager (CASI) sensor [82] over the Houston University campus in June 2012,
 350 collecting spectral information from an urban area. This scene has 114 bands and 349×1905
 351 pixels with wavelengths ranging from 380nm to 1050nm. It comprises 15 ground-truth classes
 352 (see Fig. 5).
- 353 6. Finally, the sixth dataset is **Salinas Valley**, which was also acquired by AVIRIS sensor over an
 354 agricultural area. It has 512×217 pixels and covers Salinas Valley in California. We remove the
 355 water absorption bands 108-112, 154-167 and 224, and keep 204 bands in our experiments. This
 356 scene contains 16 classes (see Fig. 5).

357 4.3. Performance evaluation

358 With the aim of evaluating the computational performance obtained by the proposed GPU
 359 implementation of SVMs for HSI data classification, and making a thorough analysis of the
 360 implemented classifiers also in terms of accuracy, several experiments have been carried out:

- 361 1. The first experiment focuses on the classification accuracy obtained by our GPU implementation
 362 as compared to a standard (CPU) implementation in LibSVM [83]. In particular, proposed

Figure 5. Number of available samples in the considered HSI datasets.

363
364

GPU-SVM has been compared with its CPU counterpart, the random forest (RF) [40] and the multinomial logistic regression (MLR) [40].

- 365 2. The second experiment focuses on the scalability and speedups achieved by the GPU
 366 implementation with regards to the CPU implementation, from a global perspective. As we
 367 pointed before, CPU1 will be considered as the baseline due its characteristics that make it the
 368 slowest device.
- 369 3. The third and last experiment focuses on some specific aspects of the GPU implementation,
 370 including data-transfer times.

371 In the following, we describe in detail the results obtained in each of the aforementioned
 372 experiments.

373 4.3.1. Experiment 1: accuracy performance

Figure 6. Classification maps for the Indian Pines dataset with the fixed training test sets in <http://dase.grss-ieee.org>. (a) False color composition. (b) Ground-truth (available labeled samples). (c) Fixed training set. (d) Fixed test set. (e) Classification map obtained by the RF classifier. (f) Classification map obtained by the MLR classifier. (g) Classification map obtained by the SVM classifier (LibSVM implementation). (h) Classification map obtained by the proposed GPU implementation. The corresponding overall classification accuracies are shown in brackets.

374 In this experiment, we use the fixed training and test data for the AVIRIS Indian Pines image
 375 [displayed in Figs. 6(c,d)], the ROSIS Pavia University image [displayed in Figs. 7(c,d)] and the
 376 University of Houston image [8(c,d)]. These fixed training and test sets are publicly available online
 377 from the IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society (GRSS) data and algorithm evaluation website
 378 (DASE) at <http://dase.grss-ieee.org>. The main rationale for using these fixed training sets is that all
 379 algorithms can be compared in a fair way, regardless of random splits of training and test sets.

380 The obtained classification results can be graphically observed in Figs. 6-8. In particular, Figs. 6(a),
 381 7(a) and 8(a) respectively show false color compositions of the aforementioned three images, while
 382 Figs. 6(b), 7(b) and 8(b) show the entire ground-truth data for each image. The results obtained by two
 383 well-known classifiers: RF [see Figs. 6(e), 7(e) and 8(e)] and the multinomial logistic regression (MLR)
 384 [see Figs. 6(f), 7(f) and 8(f)] are reported, together with the classification maps obtained by the CPU
 385 (LibSVM) implementation of the SVM [see Figs. 6(g), 7(g) and 8(g)] and our GPU implementation of

Figure 7. Classification maps for the Pavia University dataset with the fixed training test sets in <http://dase.grss-ieee.org>. (a) False color composition. (b) Ground-truth (available labeled samples). (c) Fixed training set. (d) Fixed test set. (e) Classification map obtained by the RF classifier. (f) Classification map obtained by the MLR classifier. (g) Classification map obtained by the SVM classifier (LibSVM implementation). (h) Classification map obtained by the proposed GPU implementation. The corresponding overall classification accuracies are shown in brackets..

386 SVM [see Figs. 6(h), 7(h) and 8(h)]. Although all classification maps have the typical “salt and pepper”
 387 noise of spectral classifiers, we can see that SVM classifiers achieve a higher quality map by classifying
 388 certain regions of the scenes more precisely, for instance the Soybeans-notill and Oats land-covers in
 389 Indian Pines scene or the the tree-line areas of Pavia University. Moreover, those classification maps
 390 obtained by CPU-based SVM and GPU-based SVM are quite similar.

391 The individual class accuracies are reported on Table 2. Also the overall (OA), average (AA)
 392 accuracies and kappa coefficient are shown for each HSI dataset. We can observe that the CPU and
 393 GPU implementations of the SVM classifier reach the best OA and AA percentages in all datasets,
 394 exhibiting also the best kappa value. In particular, as shown in all cases, the OA obtained by our GPU

Figure 8. Classification maps for the University of Houston dataset with the fixed training test sets in <http://dase.grss-ieee.org>. (a) False color composition. (b) Ground-truth (available labeled samples). (c) Fixed training set. (d) Fixed test set. (e) Classification map obtained by the RF classifier. (f) Classification map obtained by the MLR classifier. (g) Classification map obtained by the SVM classifier (LibSVM implementation). (h) Classification map obtained by the proposed GPU implementation. The corresponding overall classification accuracies are shown in brackets.

Table 2. Classification results obtained by different techniques for the Indian Pines, University of Pavia and University of Houston scenes, using the fixed training and test sets available for these datasets in <http://dase.grss-ieee.org>.

Class	Indian Pines				University of Pavia				Houston University			
	RF	MLR	SVM		RF	MLR	SVM		RF	MLR	SVM	
	[40]	[40]	CPU	GPU	[40]	[40]	CPU	GPU	[40]	[40]	CPU	GPU
1	32.80	68.0	88.0	88.0	79.59	77.7	83.08	81.85	82.55	82.24	82.34	82.15
2	51.56	78.07	80.74	79.32	55.2	58.78	67.45	67.2	83.5	82.5	83.36	83.36
3	44.41	59.41	67.57	67.43	45.42	67.22	64.85	65.0	97.94	99.8	99.8	99.8
4	26.46	25.25	51.52	49.9	98.73	74.29	98.28	98.35	91.46	98.3	98.96	97.86
5	79.34	88.32	87.23	86.28	99.14	98.88	99.28	99.3	96.69	97.44	98.77	98.6
6	95.71	96.89	96.61	96.67	78.77	93.52	92.06	92.3	99.16	94.41	97.9	96.78
7	20.0	50.0	100.0	100.0	80.41	85.12	88.89	88.95	75.35	73.41	77.43	75.95
8	100.0	99.2	98.8	98.8	90.96	87.58	92.12	92.31	33.03	63.82	60.3	57.78
9	16.0	40.0	60.0	50.0	97.69	99.22	96.35	96.6	69.2	70.25	76.77	77.88
10	8.47	56.14	81.71	82.03					43.9	55.6	61.29	61.56
11	89.63	81.64	86.95	87.77					69.79	74.19	80.55	81.2
12	26.6	68.44	77.66	77.94					54.12	70.41	79.92	80.65
13	89.25	96.25	93.75	94.25					59.86	67.72	70.88	72.56
14	92.0	89.95	90.64	90.83					99.35	98.79	100.0	100.0
15	38.79	82.83	76.77	81.21					97.42	95.56	96.41	97.42
16	93.64	93.18	88.64	88.64								
OA	65.69	78.16	84.21	84.25	70.15	72.23	78.91	78.67	72.97	78.98	81.86	81.69
AA	56.54	73.35	82.91	82.44	80.66	82.48	86.93	86.87	76.89	81.63	84.31	84.24
K(x100)	59.87	74.99	81.98	82.0	63.01	65.45	73.37	73.09	70.96	77.31	80.43	80.25

395 implementation of SVM is very similar to that obtained by the corresponding CPU implementation,
 396 and superior to that obtained by other well-known classifiers such as RF and MLR.

Figure 9. Processing times (and speedups) measured in the considered CPUs (CPU0 in the platform 1 and CPU1 in the platform 2) and GPUs (GPU0 in the platform 1 and GPU1 in the platform 2) as the percentage of training samples increases.

Table 3. Processing times (ms) obtained by our GPU implementation of the SVM algorithm on different platforms, using the datasets: Pavia Center and Big Indian Pines. The times indicate the transfers from host to device (HtoD), device to host (DtoH), device to device (DtoD) and the total processing times consumed by the kernels.

PAVIA CENTER								
Tr Percent	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 (laptop)				NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080Ti (desktop)			
	HtoD	DtoH	DtoD	Kernels	HtoD	DtoH	DtoD	Kernels
1	1.900800	1.008450	0.401280	89.683510	2.065540	0.909663	0.401824	53.969180
5	5.196410	1.211910	0.389169	342.75209	5.928330	1.308890	0.445162	192.82042
10	9.650360	1.710720	0.404029	588.11514	11.10364	1.798470	0.448121	292.20041
20	18.90792	2.658750	0.405595	845.38273	22.65927	2.731010	0.465384	503.46422
40	37.78842	4.761070	0.444797	1369.8100	45.99625	4.856580	0.505738	816.56403
60	56.83977	6.937100	0.483709	1924.3700	71.39292	6.930210	0.506987	1180.4300
80	77.18297	9.077530	0.476379	2425.9400	95.87500	9.032700	0.547660	1448.0500
BIG INDIAN PINES								
Tr Percent	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 (laptop)				NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080Ti (desktop)			
	HtoD	DtoH	DtoD	Kernels	HtoD	DtoH	DtoD	Kernels
1	72.270610	44.041780	20.12548	2167.8800	86.874980	45.894420	23.89330	2445.0100
5	189.45379	53.012700	21.65845	15000.320	215.96618	56.352320	25.65502	10679.120
10	345.04000	68.476270	23.63760	34717.630	395.10834	71.718340	27.34729	22486.610
20	683.13051	118.78844	29.17641	77072.650	813.34057	123.31494	32.40953	46963.590
40	1439.0210	296.14766	43.88958	184683.75	1703.9300	301.14840	46.36005	112824.33
60	2325.2100	579.43225	60.25476	335392.10	2868.1800	581.19374	61.65440	255449.66
80	3296.8700	969.39610	68.03797	519363.01	4077.2100	972.86474	77.46072	307944.21

397 4.3.2. Experiment 2: scalability and speedup

398 In this experiment, we use randomly selected training/test sets to evaluate the scalability of our
 399 GPU implementation as the amount of training becomes larger. In particular, 1%, 3%, 5%, 10%, 15%,
 400 20%, 25%, 30%, 40%, 60% and 80% of training data have been considered for University of Pavia, Pavia
 401 Center, Salinas Valley and Big Indian Pines datasets.

402 Fig 9 reports the processing times (and speedups) measured in the considered CPUs (CPU0 in
 403 the first hardware platform and CPU1 in the second platform) and GPUs (GPU0 in the platform 1
 404 and GPU1 in the platform 2) as the percentage of training increases. As we can observe in Fig. 9,
 405 for all the considered images in this experiment (University of Pavia, Pavia Center, Salinas Valley and
 406 Big Indian Pines), the processing times increase as the percentage of training samples increases. This
 407 is expected, as the complexity of the classification problem becomes larger. However, we can also

408 observe that the speedups obtained become more significant with the training size, particularly for the
 409 larger images. For instance, with University of Pavia (about 34220 pixels when training with 80% of
 410 data) the implementation is able to reach a speedup of x6 with the fastest GPU, while with Big Indian
 411 Pines (around 1315433 samples when considering 80% of training data) is x140 faster than the baseline.
 412 This indicates that our newly developed GPU implementation of SVM scales with complexity and
 413 problem size, which is a highly desirable feature in parallel implementations.

414 4.3.3. Experiment 3: GPU transfer-memory and kernel runtimes

required by the proposed GPU implementation for the Pavia Center and Big Indian Pines datasets. In all cases, the training percentage has been fixed to 40% of the available samples.

Figure 10. Memory-transfer times

415 In this experiment, we fix the training percentage to 40% and study the memory transfers required
 416 by the proposed GPU implementation for different HSI datasets over GPU0 and GPU1 devices. Here,
 417 we specifically focus on the two largest datasets (Pavia Center and Big Indian Pines) and report
 418 the memory times consumed by the considered GPU platforms. Table 3 provides a breakdown of
 419 the obtained processing times for different images and training percentages, indicating the transfer
 420 times from host to device (HtoD), device to host (DtoH), device to device (DtoD) and the time taken
 421 by the kernels. The times reported on Table 3 indicate that most of the time spent by our parallel
 422 implementation is consumed by kernels and not by data transfers, despite these transfers become more
 423 significant as the training percentage becomes larger (this does not affect scalability, as reported on
 424 Fig. 9. We can graphically observe these results in Fig. 10, where the amount of GPU video memory
 425 required by our implementation is very small in all cases (below 5.9%), which indicates that our
 426 implementation is efficient in terms of memory usage, even with large percentages of training.

427 5. Conclusions and Future Lines

428 This work presented a new GPU implementation of the well-known SVM technique in the context
 429 of HSI remote sensing data classification, with the goal of reducing computation times by massively
 430 parallelizing operations across GPU threads, and reducing memory latencies by efficiently handling

431 data read/write operations. Three experiments have been conducted over six widely-used and real
 432 HSI datasets, providing very heterogeneous information in terms of content (different land-cover
 433 classes extracted from agricultural and urban environments) and amount of data (different spatial sizes
 434 with also different spatial resolutions). These experiments show the effectiveness of our accelerated
 435 SVM implementation, which not only scales with data volume, but also with training percentage.
 436 This reveals that the acceleration is more effective when the classification problem is more complex.
 437 Moreover, the study of data transfer times and algorithmic computation times shows an efficient use
 438 of memory, where the kernel computations dominate the parallel processing times. In addition, the
 439 proposed GPU implementation achieves good performance in comparison with other popular SVM
 440 implementations, achieving similar accuracy results but with faster performance.

441 As with any new approach, there are some unresolved issues that may present challenges over
 442 time. In the future, we will improve our SVM implementation in order to reduce the accesses to
 443 global device memory and make a more efficient use of CUDA streams. In addition, we will use
 444 our accelerated SVM in conjunction with other techniques for HSI processing and classification (e.g.
 445 supervised and semi-supervised techniques) with the aim of improving even more the obtained
 446 classification results.

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